
HIVEMIND kicks-off to advance AI-powered human-centric software development

Seville, Spain – The HIVEMIND (**H**uman-centred collaborat**IV**E **M**ulti-age**N**t framework for accelerating software **D**evelopment and maintenance) project has officially kicked-off, bringing together experts from academia, industry, and research to revolutionise **software engineering** through **artificial intelligence**. Funded under the Horizon Europe programme, HIVEMIND aims to develop a responsible and human-centric approach to AI-driven software engineering, accelerating the entire software lifecycle.

About HIVEMIND

HIVEMIND introduces an innovative **LLM-based multi-agent framework** designed to enhance collaboration between human developers and AI agents. These AI agents will be specialised to support various roles within a software development team, leveraging techniques such as fine-tuning with organisational data, prompt engineering, retrieval-augmented generation, and human-in-the-loop machine learning.

This framework will drive efficiency in **smart system specification**, agile modelling, and automated requirement derivation, reducing late-stage modifications and improving consistency in software design.

The project will enable **design-by-contract programming** at all integration levels, empowering AI agents to assist in code development, analysis, verification, and testing with greater context awareness.

Extending beyond initial development, the initiative will provide robust support for **dynamic maintenance** across multi-architecture systems, ensuring long-term sustainability and adaptability in the digital landscape.

The partners

HIVEMIND is a collaborative effort uniting **13 partners** from **8 countries**, combining expertise in AI, software engineering, and industry applications. The project is coordinated by [IDENER](#) [Spain], with key contributions from [Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz](#) [Germany], [Universidad de Alicante](#) [Spain], [Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya](#) [Spain], [RISE Research Institutes of Sweden](#) [Sweden], [Software Imagination & Vision](#) [Romania], [Queen's University Belfast](#) [United Kingdom], [HAVELSAN](#) [Türkiye], [Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft](#) [Germany], [TIGA Bilgi Teknolojileri](#) [Türkiye], [AUSTRALO](#) [Estonia], [Mälardalen University](#) [Sweden], and [Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana](#) [Switzerland]. Over the next **36 months**, HIVEMIND will validate its technologies in **five real-world environments**, ensuring its impact across various societal and industrial sectors.

HIVEMIND on social media

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